

New *s*-Triazines : Synthesis of 2-Mercapto-*t*-butyl-3-*t*-butyl-4-phenylimino-5-aryl/alkyl-6-thiotetrahydro- and 2-Phenylimino-3-*t*-butyl-4-phenylimino-5-aryl/alkyl-6-thiohexahydro-1,3,5-triazines

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Several 2-mercapto-*t*-butyl-3-*t*-butyl-4-phenylimino-5-aryl/alkyl-6-thio-tetrahydro-1,3,5-triazines have been prepared by the interaction of 1-*t*-butyl-2-*S*-*t*-butyl-5-aryl/alkyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets with phenylisocyanodichloride leading to 2-phenylimino-3-*t*-butyl-4-mercapto-*t*-butyl-6-aryl/alkylimino-1,3,5-thiadiazine hydrochlorides followed by isomeric conversion of the latter with aqueous ethanolic sodium bicarbonate/sodium carbonate. These 1,3,5-triazines have been subjected to reaction of aniline affording the related-2-phenylimino-1,3,5-triazines. The imino detertbutylation and *S*-detertbutylation of both these 1,3,5-triazines with concentrated HBr and HCl and dilute HCl however, have been proved unsuccessful.

Application of *t*-butyl as a blocking group in the synthesis of nitrogen and sulphur containing compounds has been investigated earlier¹⁻³. Damle² investigated the detertbutylation reaction of certain *S*-*t*-butyl and *N*-*t*-butyl containing thiourea derivatives and observed that while *S*-detertbutylation can selectively occur with boiling dilute HCl and HBr, the *N*-detertbutylation can only be achieved with boiling concentrated HCl or HBr. In view of our interest in the synthesis of new 1,3,5-triazines having *S*-*t*-butyl and *N*-*t*-butyl groups have been synthesised by the interaction of 2-*S*-*t*-butyliso-1-*t*-butyl-5-aryl-2,4-dithiobiurets⁶ (5) and phenylisocyanodichloride^{4,5} (Scheme 1). However, detertbutylation from both S and N of the 1,3,5-triazines with boiling concentrated HCl and HBr proved unsuccessful.

Reaction of *N*-phenylisocyanodichloride and 1-*t*-butyl-2-*S*-*t*-butyl-5-phenyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (5a) (Table 1) produced a yellow acidic solid, m.p. 122°d. It was found highly hygroscopic and therefore could not be exposed to atmosphere for longer time. It was found desulphurisable when boiled with alkaline plumbite solution. Its ethanolic solution

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|-------------------------|-----------------------------|
| a ; R = Phenyl | e ; R = <i>m</i> -Cl-Phenyl |
| b ; R = <i>o</i> -Tolyl | f ; R = <i>p</i> -Cl-Phenyl |
| c ; R = <i>m</i> -Tolyl | g ; R = Ethyl |
| d ; R = <i>p</i> -Tolyl | h ; R = <i>t</i> -Butyl |

Scheme 1

when heated with alcoholic picric acid. a picrate crystallised from hot ethanol (m.p. 162°) was obtained. This product when boiled with 5% ethanolic aqueous solution of sodium bicarbonate/sodium carbonate, afforded a solid, m.p. 182°. This product was not acidic in nature. It was also not desulphurisable when boiled with alkaline plumbite solution. On thermal decomposition smells of phenylisothiocyanate and t-butylmercaptan were clearly detected. The ir spectrum of the product indicated the bands at 1610 (C=N), 1150 (C-S) and two bands⁷ at 1550 and 790 cm⁻¹ indicating the presence of s-triazine structure.

TABLE 1-2-S-t-BUTYL-1-t-BUTYL-5-ARYL/ALKYL-2,4-ISODITHIOBIURETS (5)*

Aryl/alkyl isothiocyanate (g)	2,4-Isodithiobiuret (g)	Decomp temp °C
4a(1.3)	5a(2.0)	182
b(1.6)	b(2.2)	174
c(1.6)	c(2.3)	169
d(1.6)	d(2.5)	179
e(1.8)	e(2.6)	165
f(1.8)	f(2.5)	178
g(1.28)	g(2.1)	164
h(1.3)	h(2.2)	177

*Reactants 2-S-t-Butyl-1-t-butylisothiocarbamide (3, 0.01 mol), aryl/alkylisothiocyanate (4, 0.01 mol), reaction medium: acetone, all compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and S analyses

One more band at 1220 cm⁻¹ indicated the presence of t-butyl group. The ¹H nmr spectra showed singals at δ 1.35 (N-t-butyl protons), 6.7-7.3 (ArH)^{7,8} and 3.0 (probably S-t-butyl protons). Its mass spectrum did not show the parent radical ion. On the basis of all the above facts the unstable product with m.p. 122°d was assigned the structure 2-phenylimino-3-t-butyl-4-mercapto-t-butyl-6-phenylimino-dihydro-1,3,5-thiadiazine hydrochloride (6a), and the product with m.p. 182°d was assigned as 2-mercapto-t-butyl-3-t-butyl-4-phenylimino-5-phenyl-6-thio-tetrahydro-1,3,5-triazines (1a).

On extending the reaction of phenylisocyanodichloride to several other 2,4-isodithiobiurets (5b-h) the corresponding unstable 1,3,5-thiadiazine hydro-

chlorides (6b-h) have been isolated. All these have been isomerised into the corresponding 1,3,5-triazines (1b-h) on treatment with aqueous ethanolic sodium bicarbonate (Table 2).

TABLE 2-2-MERCAPTO-t-BUTYL-3-t-BUTYL-4-PHENYLIMINO-5-ARYL/ALKYL-6-THIOTETRAHYDRO-1,3,5-TRIAZINES (1)*

2,4-Isodithiobiuret (g)	1,3,5-Thiadiazine-hydrochloride (g)	Decomp temp °C	1,3,5-Triazine (g)	Mp °C
5a(3.2)	6a(2.8)	122	1a(1.8)	182
b(3.3)	b(2.9)	136	b(1.9)	170
c(3.3)	c(2.8)	120	c(2.0)	165
d(3.3)	d(3.0)	116	d(2.1)	164
e(3.5)	e(2.8)	124	e(2.0)	164
f(3.5)	f(2.9)	120	f(2.1)	166
g(2.7)	g(2.5)	114	g(1.6)	180
h(2.9)	h(2.8)	126	h(1.9)	208

*Reactants 2-S-t-Butyl-1-t-butyl-5-aryl/alkyl-2,4-isodithiobiuret (5, 0.01 mol), N-phenylisocyanodichloride (0.01 mol, 2 g), reaction medium: chloroform (for 6), aqueous ethanolic sodium bicarbonate/sodium carbonate (for 1), all compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and S analyses

One more possible structure 7a, can arise by totally different bond rearrangement in 6. But this possibility is ruled out. Structure 1 is further confirmed for the reaction product on the basis of thermal decomposition of 1c and 1f where evolution of p-tolyl and p-Cl-phenyl isothiocyanates have been observed. The corresponding 7c and 7f can not form these isothiocyanates.

Compound 1a reacted with aniline in boiling ethanolic medium eliminating t-butylmercaptan and produced a new product, m.p. 175°. The product was non-desulphurisable on boiling with alkaline plumbite solution. On thermal decomposition and smell of phenyl isothiocyanate was clearly detected. The ir spectrum of the product showed presence of bands at 3360 (NH), 1610 (C=N), 1050 (C=S), 1570 and 790 (1,3,5-triazine)⁷ and 1220 cm⁻¹ (t-butyl group). The nmr spectrum showed the signals at δ 1.3 (N-t-butyl protons), 7.0 (ArH)^{7,8} and 7.5 (-CS-NH). Therefore, the product with m.p. 175°, was assigned structure 2,4-diphenylimino-3-t-butyl-5-phenyl-6-thiohexahydro-1,3,5-triazine (2a) (Table 3).

The reaction of aniline was also extended to other 2-mercapto-*t*-butyl-1,3,5-triazines (**1b–h**) and the corresponding 2-phenylimino-1,3,5-triazines (**2b, d and h** only) isolated as solids. Compounds **2c, e, f** and **g** were obtained as semi-solid which could not be characterised.

TABLE 3—2-PHENYLIMINO-3-*t*-BUTYL-4-PHENYLIMINO-5-ARYL/ALKYL-6-THIOHEXAHYDRO-1,3,5-TRIAZINES (**2**)*

5-Aryl/alkyl-1,3,5-triazine (g)	2-Phenylimino-5-aryl/alkyl-1,3,5-triazine (g)	M p °C
1a (4 0)	2a (3 8)	175
b (4 4)	b (3 2)	250
c (4 4)	c	Semi-solid
d (4 4)	d (3 4)	290
e (4 5)	e	Semi-solid
f (4 5)	f	Semi-solid
g (3 0)	g	Semi-solid
h (3 6)	h (3 2)	164

*Reactants : 2-Mercapto-*t*-butyl-3-*t*-butyl-4-phenylimino-5-aryl/alkyl-6-thiohexahydro-1,3,5-triazine (**1**; 0.01 mol), aniline (0.01 mol), medium : boiling ethanol; all compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and S analyses.

Deimino-*t*-butylation and *S*-detertbutylation of **1** and **2** and **1** were attempted in boiling concentrated HBr and HCl and dilute HCl respectively, but without success. In all the cases semi-solids were isolated which could not be converted into granular solid by the usual procedures.

Experimental

N-Phenylisocyanodichloride was prepared by the usual procedure^{4,5}.

2-*S-t*-Butyl-1-*t*-butyl-5-aryl/alkyl-2,4-isodithiobiu-*rets* (**5**)⁶ : Details of a typical experiment (where R = phenyl; **5a**) are as follows. To an acetone solution (20 ml) of 2-*S-t*-butyl-1-*t*-butyl isothiocarbamide (0.01 mol, 1.8 g) was added phenyl isothiocyanate (0.01 mol, 1.3 g) and the mixture was refluxed over a boiling water-bath for 3 h. Acetone was then distilled off and the resulting solid (2.0 g) was crystallised from hot ethanol, m.p. 182°d (Found : N, 12.80; S, 20.00. C₁₆H₂₅N₃S₂ requires : N, 13.00; S, 19.8%).

2-Mercapto-*t*-butyl-3-*t*-butyl-4-phenylimino-5-aryl/alkyl-6-thiotetrahydro-1,3,5-triazines (**1a**) : Details of a typical preparation (where R = phenyl; **1a**) are as follows. To a chloroform suspension (20 ml) of **5a** (0.01 mol, 3.2 g), a chloroform solution (20 ml) of *N*-phenylisocyanodichloride (0.01 mol, 2 g) was added and the mixture was kept for 10 h. During the reaction evolution of HCl was noticed. The separated semi-solid was triturated several times with petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) to yield a yellow acidic product (**6a**; 2.8 g), m.p. 122°d (Found : N, 11.9, S, 14.10. C₂₃H₂₈N₄S₂.HCl requires: N, 12.16, S, 13.8%).

Compound **6a** (2.8 g) when boiled with aqueous 5% ethanolic sodium bicarbonate/sodium carbonate for 3 h afforded a solid (**1a**; 1.8 g) crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 122° (Found : C, 88.28, H, 6.4; N, 13.0., S, 15.2. C₂₃H₂₈N₄S₂ requires : C, 88.67; H, 6.6; N, 13.20; S, 15.09%).

2,4-Diphenylimino-3-*t*-butyl-5-aryl/alkyl-6-thiohexahydro-1,3,5-triazines (**2**) : Details of a typical experiment (where aryl = phenyl; **2a**) are as follows. A mixture of **1a** (0.01 mol, 4.0 g) and aniline (0.01 mol, 0.9 g) and ethanol (25 ml) was refluxed over a boiling water-bath for 3 h. The resultant clear solution was cooled and the separated solid (**2a**; 3.8 g) was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 175° (Found : C, 70.0; H, 5.3; N, 16.5; S, 7.8, C₂₅H₂₅N₅S requires : C, 70.2; H, 5.8; N, 16.3; S, 7.4%).

References

1. G. V. NAIR, *Indian J Chem.*, 1966, **4**, 516.
2. M. H. DAMLE, Ph.D. Thesis, Nagpur University, 1976.
3. N. K. KHANDELWAL, B. N. BERAD and M. G. PARANJPE, *J Indian Chem Soc.*, 1987, **64**, 321.
4. P. P. PATHE and M. G. PARANJPE, *Indian J Chem., Sect B*, 1981, **20**, 824.
5. P. P. PATHE and M. G. PARANJPE, *J Indian Chem Soc.*, 1984, **61**, 149.
6. V. K. VERMA, *Indian J Chem.*, 1963, **1**, 300.
7. N. B. COLTHUP, H. L. DALY and S. E. WEBERLEY, "Introduction to Ir and Raman Spectroscopy", Academic, New York, 1964.
8. R. M. SILVERSTEIN, G. C. BASSLER and T. C. MORRIL, "Spectroscopic Identification of Organic Compounds", Wiley, New York, 1981.

